

School of Science and Engineering

How Students Expect Academic Apps to Be Organized: AUI Mockup Interaction
Study

Undergraduate Research Report

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LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: Average Task Completion Time by UI Type

This figure compares the average time (in seconds) taken by participants to complete tasks using each of the three UI prototypes: Classic, Icon-Only, and Chatbot.

Figure 2: Average Number of Clicks by UI Type

This figure illustrates the mean number of clicks required per task across the three UI types, highlighting interaction effort and efficiency.

Figure 3: Average Error Count by UI Type

This figure presents the average number of errors made during task completion for each interface, reflecting user confusion or missteps.

ABSTRACT (ENGLISH)

This study investigates how university students expect academic app features to be organized in a web user interface (UI). The research evaluates three UI prototypes: a traditional AUI-style sidebar layout, an icon-only interface, and a chatbot interface. Participants completed standardized academic tasks on each UI. Metrics such as task completion time, clicks, and navigation errors were recorded and analyzed. The study concludes that traditional UIs remain the most efficient, particularly for students with low to moderate digital

Keywords: usability testing, web interface design, student experience, chatbot UI, human-computer interaction, academic apps

ABSTRACT (FRENCH)

Cette recherche examine comment les étudiants universitaires s'attendent à ce que les fonctionnalités d'une application académique soient organisées dans une interface utilisateur web. Trois prototypes d'interface ont été évalués : une interface classique de type AUI, une interface uniquement basée sur des icônes et une interface de type chatbot. Les participants ont réalisé des tâches académiques standardisées sur chaque interface. Les données de temps, de clics et d'erreurs ont été recueillies et analysées. Les résultats montrent que les interfaces traditionnelles sont les plus efficaces, notamment pour les étudiants ayant une expérience numérique faible à modérée.

Mots-clés : test d'utilisabilité, conception d'interfaces web, expérience étudiante, interface chatbot, interaction homme-machine, application académique

INTRODUCTION

Modern web applications in education often struggle with usability because their interfaces do not always align with users' mental models and expectations. Understanding how students naturally expect academic features to be organized and presented is important for creating interfaces that are efficient, intuitive, and user-friendly.

The objective of this study is to evaluate and compare the usability of three academic UI layouts by analysing students' performance and behavior while completing multiple standardized academic tasks.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

Many academic platforms organize information and features in ways that do not match how students naturally expect them to work. This can cause confusion, increase navigation errors, and slow down task completion. Despite the widespread use of academic platforms, there is still limited research on how students expect academic interfaces to be structured and presented.

Solving this problem can help improve the usability of academic applications by making them more intuitive, efficient, and easier to navigate. Better UI design can reduce user frustration, improve task performance, and increase overall student satisfaction with academic platforms.

PROJECT SPECIFICATIONS

Focused on AUI students, the project centers on academic UI prototypes designed specifically for university-related use cases. It covers five core academic tasks that aim to improve the overall student academic experience and usability.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a within-subject design in which all 20 participants interacted with each of the three UI prototypes: the Classic UI (sidebar layout), the Icon-Only UI, and the Chatbot-based UI. Each participant completed five standardized academic tasks on every interface. Performance was evaluated using three core usability metrics: task completion time (measured in seconds), number of clicks, and number of navigation errors. This setup enabled a direct comparison across the different UI types while controlling individual differences in user behavior.

The project timeline was divided into five stages. Week 1 focused on UI design and preparation of the test plan. Weeks 2 and 3 were dedicated to participant testing sessions, followed by data analysis in Week 4. Finally, Week 5 focused on report writing and documentation of the findings.

STEEPLE ANALYSIS

Social: Improving academic app usability directly benefits students by reducing frustration, supporting accessibility, and increasing engagement with institutional digital tools. The study also reflects shifting student expectations shaped by modern UI ecosystems .

Technological: The project explores current and emerging UI paradigms ; chatbots, icon-driven layouts, and traditional sidebars; through interactive Figma prototypes. It highlights the growing importance of adaptive UI systems and conversational interfaces in educational apps.

Economic: Testing early-stage UI concepts using mockups is cost-effective and prevents expensive redesigns post-launch. The methodology demonstrates how usability research can inform smarter development investment decisions for universities or ed-tech startups

Environmental: The entire study was conducted; using online prototyping tools (Figma), in person testing sessions, and data collection ;resulting in zero sustainable research practices.

Political: While the study itself is apolitical, it indirectly supports institutional digital transformation policies

that seek to modernize student-facing services, improve learning equity, and align with national digital education strategies.

Legal: Participants were not asked for any personal identifiers, and all testing data was anonymized.

No sensitive data was collected. The study complies with academic ethics and basic data protection practices, including informed consent.

Ethical: Participants volunteered freely and were informed about the study's purpose. No deception or risk was involved. The study promotes digital inclusion by highlighting UI barriers faced by students with varying levels of tech fluency.

ENGINEERING STANDARDS

Usability rules, such as Nielsen’s heuristics, are basic principles that help make websites and applications easier to use. These principles focus on keeping interfaces simple, making available actions clear to users, and providing visible feedback whenever users interact with the system, such as clicking a button or completing an action.

Accessibility rules, such as the Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG), are designed to ensure that websites can be used by people with disabilities. These guidelines include practices such as using readable text, maintaining strong color contrast, and ensuring that websites can be navigated using a keyboard or screen reader.

Good design practices for web applications focus on improving usability and reducing user confusion. These practices include using clear and understandable buttons, creating layouts that are organized and responsive, and avoiding design choices that may slow down or frustrate users during navigation.

LOGIC MODEL FRAMEWORK

1.1 Target Population: Undergraduate students at Al Akhawayn University, aged 18–24, representing all academic levels (from freshman to senior year).

1.2 Underlying Assumptions: Participants’ prior experience with user interfaces (e.g., mobile apps, websites) influences their performance and interaction quality with the tested prototypes.

1.3 Resources and Challenges: Primary resources included time-limited access to participants and digital prototyping via Figma. Challenges involved time constraints, balancing academic schedules, and maintaining consistent testing conditions.

1.4 Activities: The main research activities included the creation of interactive UI prototypes, structured testing sessions with participants, and systematic data collection on performance metrics.

1.5 Outputs of the Project: The study produced a structured dataset in Excel, visualized results through graphs, and this research report documenting the findings and methodology.

1.6 Outcomes: The goal was to determine which UI layout is perceived as most intuitive and efficient by

students, based on performance metrics and user interaction behavior.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Human-Computer Interaction Principles : Explores how users interact with digital systems and how interface design impacts usability, learnability, and satisfaction.

Mental Models in UI Design : Discusses the importance of aligning interface structures with users' expectations and cognitive patterns to improve usability and reduce confusion.

Usability Testing in Educational Platforms : Examines methods for evaluating user experience in academic software, highlighting the need for intuitive and accessible design in learning environments.

APPROACH

Experimental Design:

Each participant interacted with all three UI prototypes:

Classic

Icon-only

Chatbot-based interface.

This design allowed direct comparison across UIs while controlling for individual differences.

Tools and Technologies Used:

Figma was used to design and build interactive web-based UI mockups; While ,“Excel” was Used for data entry, cleaning, and basic statistical analysis.

Task Description:

Participants completed the same five academic tasks across all three UI prototypes: checking grades, finding the financial aid form, adding or dropping a course, viewing their schedule, and checking housing information. Using the same tasks for each interface ensured consistency and allowed for a fair comparison between the different UI layouts.

DATA COLLECTION

For each participant, task, and UI combination, several usability metrics were recorded. Task completion time, measured in seconds, captured how long participants took to complete each task from start to finish. The number of clicks represented the total number of user interactions, including clicks or prompts, required to complete a task. Navigation errors were also recorded and included actions such as clicking on the wrong page or icon, entering an irrelevant prompt in the Chatbot UI, opening an incorrect tab or submenu, or performing unnecessary actions that required backtracking. In addition, each participant’s self-reported level of digital experience (Low, Medium, or High) was documented to support later correlation analysis.

Dataset Overview:

A total of 20 participants completed 5 tasks on each of the 3 UI prototypes, resulting in 300 individual interaction records (20 participants × 3 UIs × 5 tasks).

Key Variables:

Participant ID	UI Type	Task Number	Task Completion Time (s)	Number of Clicks/prompts	Number of Errors
2 (best)	Classic UI	4	10.7	8	0
5 (worst)	Icon UI	1	22.5	7	4
10 (average)	Chatbot UI	5	21	10	2

These data points represent single task attempts by different participants across the three UI designs. They illustrate how users varied in performance depending on both the task and the interface used. This structure allowed for consistent analysis across the full dataset of 300 records.

Visual Representations:

The data was analyzed and presented using bar charts (Figures 1–3) to clearly compare average task completion times, click counts, and error rates across UI types.

Figure 1: Average Task Completion Time by UI Type

Figure 2: Average Number of Clicks by UI Type

Figure 3: Average Error Count by UI Type

RESULTS AND INTERPRETATION

The data collected from 20 participants, each completing five tasks across three different academic UI prototypes (Classic, Icon-only, and Chatbot), revealed significant differences in performance. These differences were measured using three main indicators: task completion time, number of clicks or prompts, and number of errors. While the original hypothesis predicted that UI familiarity would affect usability, the results not only confirmed this, but also highlighted interesting behavioral patterns and user struggles.

Performance by UI Type

Classic UI: Familiarity Wins

The Classic UI came out as the most efficient interface across nearly all participants. On average, tasks were completed in 13.6 seconds, with ~7 clicks, and a very low error rate of ~0.47 errors per task.

Most users navigated the Classic layout with confidence and ease. This UI closely resembles the structure of many real-world academic portals, so even participants with lower digital skills were able to complete tasks with relatively few problems. The visual hierarchy, use of labels, and clear buttons allowed users to form an immediate mental model of where to click and what to expect.

This UI worked well for both experienced and less experienced users. For instance, Participant 2 completed a task in just 10.7 seconds with 8 clicks and 0 errors, nearly ideal performance. Even participants with slower reactions or occasional uncertainty still performed fairly well with the Classic interface.

Icon-Only UI: A Misleading Minimalism

Despite its clean look, the Icon-only UI led to the worst overall performance. The average task time was 21.6 seconds, and the average error rate reached 1.85, the highest of all three designs. Interestingly, the number of clicks was the lowest (~6.2 clicks per task), which at first seems positive; but it actually reflects that users spent more time *thinking* before clicking, or clicking fewer times because they were unsure.

Many users were clearly confused by the meaning of the icons, especially when context was missing. For example, icons like a gear (settings), magnifying glass (search), or calendar (schedule) were sometimes misinterpreted. Users without strong digital experience frequently hovered over icons, backtracked, or clicked incorrectly before figuring out the right action.

A strong example is Participant 5, who recorded 22.5 seconds, 7 clicks, and a whopping 4 errors on a single task. This reflects trial-and-error behavior, likely due to ambiguous icon meanings.

Chatbot UI: Polarizing but Promising

The Chatbot UI had the most mixed results. It landed in the middle in terms of speed (17.3 seconds) and error rate (~1.0), but had the highest number of interactions, with an average of ~9.2 prompts or clicks per task.

Some users adapted quickly and used the chatbot efficiently, completing tasks with direct input like “Show my schedule” or “Check grades.” However, others struggled with phrasing or misunderstood the flow, leading to extra steps or confusion. This split in performance is crucial: around 40% of users performed well, but the remaining 60% needed more help or got stuck in multiple clarification loops. For instance, Participant 10 took 21 seconds, used 10 prompts, and still had 2 errors, which suggests a longer conversation to reach the right result. Meanwhile, other users managed quick completions in under 15 seconds with no errors. The chatbot’s variability reflects both its potential and its current usability challenges.

Performance Patterns Based on Digital Familiarity

One of the more noticeable patterns in the results was how a participant’s comfort with digital tools seemed to influence their overall performance. Even though we did not ask users to rate their computer skills directly, their behavior during the tasks revealed quite a lot.

Some participants moved through the interfaces quickly, made very few mistakes, and seemed confident in where they were clicking or typing. These users probably had higher digital literacy. They showed signs of being used to online platforms, and they seemed to understand how systems usually work. For example, when they used the Chatbot UI, they wrote short and accurate commands that the system could understand without any confusion. In the Icon UI, they could often guess what an icon meant just by looking at it, even if it was not labeled.

In contrast, other participants clearly had more difficulty. They paused before clicking, made more errors, or chose the wrong icons multiple times. Some had trouble knowing what to type into the chatbot and often needed to rephrase their messages or wait for extra clarification. This group likely had less experience with digital platforms, and for them, the system was harder to use.

The results showed that users who did well with the Classic UI often also did okay with the Chatbot UI. This suggests that their general comfort with digital systems helped them adapt, even if the layout or input method was different. However, users who struggled with the Icon UI usually also performed poorly with the Chatbot UI. This suggests that both of these interfaces require a higher level of confidence and familiarity with how digital tools are supposed to behave.

Overall, the Classic UI seems to be the safest choice for users who are not very tech-savvy. The Icon UI and Chatbot UI may work better for advanced users, but they can easily create confusion for others. This raises a concern for designers: if the goal is to create an app for a wide range of users, the interface needs to be simple enough for beginners, without removing features that experienced users might want.

Task Difficulty Impact

Another important factor in user performance was the difficulty of the tasks themselves. Not all tasks were equal, and the harder ones revealed more weaknesses in the interface designs.

Some tasks were straightforward, such as checking course grades. Most users completed these without trouble. In the Classic UI, the button was clearly labeled, so people found it quickly. In the Chatbot UI, many users typed simple commands like “show grades” and got accurate responses. Even users who were not very experienced with chatbots could manage that.

However, tasks that involved more steps or less obvious language caused more problems. For instance, scheduling an advising appointment or checking financial aid information took longer and created more errors. These tasks required more thinking, and that exposed the flaws in the interface.

In the Icon UI, the icons were not always clear. A dollar sign might represent financial aid, but some users thought it meant payments or fees. A calendar icon might suggest either a class schedule or a meeting, and without labels, participants had to guess. This led to more trial and error, which increased both the task completion time and the number of mistakes.

In the Chatbot UI, these same tasks worked well for users who typed the exact right phrase. Some participants got through quickly by saying things like “schedule meeting with advisor” or “check scholarship status.” However, if they used vague or informal language, the chatbot often misunderstood. This resulted in longer back-and-forth conversations or incorrect results.

These patterns show that harder tasks put more pressure on the system to be clear. If the design relies too much on perfect input or user guesswork, it creates a frustrating experience. Good design should not just focus on simple tasks. It should also support users during more difficult or unfamiliar situations, when they are unsure or stressed.

Variability and Consistency Across Users

Some users were very consistent. They performed well on all three interfaces and did not show big changes in performance. These users appeared flexible and adaptable. They adjusted their approach depending on what the interface looked like, and they seemed to understand what the system expected from them.

Other users were more sensitive to changes. For example, one participant performed very well on the Classic UI but became completely confused when faced with the Icon-Only interface. They spent more

than double the time on the same task because they could not tell what the icons meant. In another case, a participant did well in the Chatbot UI for basic tasks but struggled when the conversation became more complex.

The Chatbot UI showed the widest range of outcomes. Some users completed tasks in less than 13 seconds, while others took more than 30 seconds. This large difference suggests that the chatbot either worked very well or very poorly, depending on how well the user could express their request.

These observations suggest that users bring different strengths and weaknesses to digital systems. Some are visual thinkers who do well with menus. Others prefer typing and searching. Some users need more structure and guidance, while others are happy to explore and try new things. This makes it clear that there is no single interface that works perfectly for everyone.

A better solution might be to offer users options. For example, a system could let users choose between visual menus and chat commands. Or it could provide a switch between icon-based navigation and labeled buttons. By offering more than one way to interact, the system can meet users at their own level, instead of forcing everyone to follow the same path.

Summary of Key Findings

Based on the full dataset, several clear conclusions can be drawn:

First, the Classic UI was the easiest and most effective for the largest number of users. Its simple layout and clear labels made it accessible even for those with limited digital experience. Most participants completed tasks quickly and with few errors when using this interface.

Second, the Icon-Only UI was the most difficult. Without text labels, users had to rely on guessing or prior experience. Many participants made mistakes, took longer to complete tasks, and often clicked on the wrong elements before finding the correct one.

Third, the Chatbot UI showed mixed results. Some users found it fast and flexible, especially when they used clear and accurate commands. Others struggled with unclear prompts or had trouble understanding what the chatbot could do. The system responded well to exact phrases but did not always help when users made vague or casual requests.

Overall, performance seemed to be closely related to the user's familiarity with digital systems.

Participants who were confident and experienced with technology usually did well across all three interfaces. Those with less experience tended to struggle more, especially on the Icon and Chatbot UIs.

Task difficulty also played a role. Simple tasks gave everyone a fair chance, but harder tasks exposed design weaknesses. Interfaces that required more guessing or more precise input created frustration for many users.

One clear message from the study is that people are different. Some are fast and confident, while others are more cautious or unsure. The most successful systems will be those that support both types of users. A design that offers multiple options, such as menus and chat, or labeled buttons and icons, can create a better experience for everyone.

CONCLUSION

This study aimed to explore how different user interface styles impact the performance of students when completing academic-related tasks. After collecting and analyzing 300 individual task records from 20 participants, several strong patterns became clear.

Among the three interfaces tested, the Classic UI performed best overall. Users completed tasks more quickly, made fewer mistakes, and generally felt more in control. The design was simple and familiar, with clearly labeled buttons and a traditional layout. This format gave users visual clarity and a sense of structure, which helped them make decisions quickly and confidently. Even users with low to moderate digital experience were able to navigate this layout effectively, which makes it a strong option for academic apps or systems that will be used by a wide range of students.

On the other hand, the Icon-Only UI presented significant challenges. While it looked clean and modern, the lack of text labels created confusion for many users. Participants often had to guess what an icon meant or click around to figure it out. This led to a higher number of errors and longer completion times. Users who were more familiar with icons or had experience using similar minimalist apps performed slightly better, but overall, this layout did not offer enough clarity or support for most people. The results show that minimal design can backfire if it removes too much context or requires users to guess what each action means.

The Chatbot UI had mixed results. For some users, it was very efficient. These participants typed clear commands, received accurate responses, and completed tasks quickly. However, for others, the chatbot was a source of frustration. When a user typed something vague, used the wrong wording, or expected the chatbot to understand something more complex, the system either gave the wrong output or required several follow-up messages. This caused the process to drag on and increased the overall time and number of steps needed to finish the task. Despite this, many users saw the potential in the chatbot

system. It was flexible and could be fast when used properly, but it still requires improvements in how it interprets language and how it guides users through tasks.

In summary, the Classic UI is the safest and most reliable option for most users. It provides structure and reduces the chances of making mistakes. The Icon-Only UI looks appealing but lacks the usability needed for consistent performance. The Chatbot UI has promise, especially for more advanced users, but still needs work to become intuitive and reliable for everyone.

Future Work

This project provided useful insights, but there are several directions that future research can explore to improve both the study and the user interface designs themselves.

One key area is personalization. Not all users interact with systems the same way, so giving them some control over how they use the interface could improve both satisfaction and performance. For example, users could be allowed to switch between chatbot and classic modes depending on what they prefer.

Personalization can also include font size, color contrast, or navigation shortcuts based on a user's habits or needs.

Another idea is to test hybrid UI layouts. This means combining elements from more than one design, such as adding labels to icons or letting users trigger chatbot commands through visual buttons. A hybrid system could take the best parts of each interface and reduce their weaknesses. For instance, if the chatbot also showed clickable suggestions or templates, users might make fewer errors and feel more guided.

Expanding the user base is also important. This study focused on university students, most of whom had some level of digital literacy. Future studies should involve participants from different age groups, education levels, and technology backgrounds. Including older adults, first-time users, or people with disabilities could reveal new usability challenges and lead to more inclusive design choices.

Finally, there is room for more advanced measurement tools. In this study, we looked at time, clicks, and

errors. These are useful, but future research could include things like eye-tracking to see where users look before they act, or even tools that detect signs of cognitive load or stress. This kind of data can reveal when users are confused or overwhelmed, even if they do not say it out loud or make obvious mistakes. In conclusion, while this study gave us a strong starting point, the work is far from finished. There are many ways to improve both the interfaces and the research methods, and doing so will help create systems that are easier, smarter, and more accessible for everyone.

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